

**TRADUZIONE ED ESPRESSIONI POLIREMATICHE.
UNO STUDIO CONTRASTIVO ITALIANO-ROMENO /
TRANSLATION AND POLYREOMATIC EXPRESSIONS.
A CONTRASTIVE STUDY BETWEEN ITALIAN AND ROMANIAN**

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In the formation of the loan translations, the correct equivalence of the polyrematic expressions from the source language to the target language is very important and it can be supported by the parallelism between the two languages. But in the case of closely related languages, there is a clear distinction between the loan translation and the parallelism or the equivalence, and this can lead to a confusion between the two linguistic phenomena. Our analysis of the interferences between two Romance languages, Italian and Romanian, allowed us to make an inventory of a number of polyrematic expressions referring to the parts of the human body. Among all types of loan translation, the phraseological one seems to be clearly the most common.